

Handout, Assignment ... Saving Lives: Speculative Analysis on #theCoIncidence of #AsthmaHospitalizations and #COVID-19Disease, ... Ongoing Reflections on Sars-CoV-2, A Compromised Immune System and Risk Assessment, ¹

December 26, 2025

Dear All, Thank you for contributing to this re-design of the course Cancer Prevention acknowledging the era of SARS-CoV- 2² infections responsible for the disease COVID-19 and the potential role of a compromised Immune System in the progress of an infection, disease. We are also covering the role of a compromised Immune System in the progress of metastatic cancer. *I hope we will become interested in causation stories*, proofs of things. Another hope is we form collaborations. One of the aims of this course is to encourage you to always be an analyst. Your presence has helped me push the renaming of the course for Spring 2023: *Prevention Research: Lights and Shadows in Viral Infections and Cancer*.

Please check this out, I like the repository Zenodo a lot, established by the EU at CERN and open to all. ... I placed the paper you are reading now there: Moses, K. Handout: Assignment - Saving Lives, Speculative Reasoning on #theCoIncidence of #Asthma Hospitalizations and #COVID-19 Disease. Ongoing Reflections on Sars-CoV-2, A Compromised Immune System and Risk Assessment, (Version Draft_4). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4107132>
Thanks,

Assignment: Why do you think a Health Disparity Border exists and how would you investigate it? Please see below,

Keywords: #CoIncidence #HealthBorders #HealthDisparities #AsthmaHospitalizations #SarCoV2 #COVID-19Disease #ImmuneSystem #HealthDisparities #Harlem

- If we raise the *Science of Health*³ we should embrace the current health crisis, COVID-19 Disease. Some of us are encountering the novel virus and not surviving and some of us are surviving. Death, Survival appears to be a reveal on *the conditions of our lives and the potentially compromised state of our Immune Systems*. The survivors can provide *plasma* that contains antibodies and killer T-cells that neutralize the novel Coronavirus. I hope our course will help you move towards speculative reasoning and writing. It is always worth starting because we have visible, un-remedied Health Disparities. *Theory 1*: the survivors have an *uncompromised Immune System*⁴ which is critically important to our defences against invading viruses, bacteria and cancer cells, and, e.g., builds over time a successful immune response to Sars-CoV-2 and cells infected with Sars-CoV-2. *Theory 2*: the asymptomatic survivors have an uncompromised Immune System which is critically important to our defences against

¹ Published to Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4107131> by K Moses JD PhD - reach me at K.Moses@outlook.com

² Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus Clade 2 ... Find NCBI SARS-CoV-2 literature, sequence, and clinical content here <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sars-cov-2/>.

³ Is the telling of a human health story, the telling of reducing injuries to the Immune System, e.g., lowering the incidence of DNA Injury, premature Telomere shortening, Deleterious Mutations with safer environments and more dietary health interventions? Less Stress in all its forms? ... For background see here http://bit.ly/AssignedReading_WallsOfDeath, the reading includes the paper <http://bitly.com/Wachteretal2013>.

⁴ *Compromised Immune Systems*

invading viruses, bacteria and cancer cells and produces or builds an immune response that suppresses, e.g., **Sars-CoV-2** before symptoms can arise. Our course will focus on the **Immune System**, its relevance to defending us. We will consider the role of telomere length in the journey to a compromised Immune System.

Introducing Causality - Thinking Causal Framework

- **Causal Inference** – the process of drawing a conclusion about the effect of an exposure on an outcome is foundational to Public Health and Environmental Protection where it is used by the school of thought I hope we will join to guide new interventions for screening and precautionary policies. Think **Flint**, see ‘US judge approves \$626m water settlement for Flint, Michigan.’ Al Jazeera, 11 Nov. 2021, www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/11/11/us-judge-approves-626m-water-settlement-for-flint-michigan. ...a showing of why **precaution** is vital.
- In this course⁵ we are taking **the role of observers and reviewers**, I propose we also adopt a topic in Causal Inference called ‘**transportability**’, to quote a good working description we could use this in our practice: ‘**transferring causal knowledge collected in several heterogeneous domains to a target domain in which [there are / were] only passive observations and limited experimental data [][could] be collected.**’^{6,7 8 9}
- I have tried to steer us to explicitly deciding on what are critical observations for our health and environment status. This is effectively looking for what things - the exposures - correlate to our health - the outcomes. **Looking for the correlates,**
- I propose we adopt **Popper’s View**, a deductivist view, when our theories (hypotheses, models) make predictions found not to be a reality, the theories need rejecting or modifying or a designing restart. *Our theories are also our guides for the how and which data to collect (Darwin’s guiding notes on methods). Darwin advised us that without a theory you might as well count the stones on Brighton Beach, England.*¹⁰ I propose we **look for the correlates using a theory to guide our looking.** If our looking / collecting of data identifies our reasoning as flawed, then our theories need rejecting or modifying or a design restart. It is likely our theories will depend on exposure and outcome observations and the consistency of the observations. Our theories are ideas on situations that have yet to be proven, our work is to move closer to emergent truths. If **Consistency** of the observations supporting the Theory appears to identify the Theory as a valid explainer of

Figure 1: Hey ya, ... ‘3000, for the sake of everyone in the band, act like you got some sense.’

⁵ **The conditions of our lives,**

⁶ Elias Bareinboim and Judea Pearl. Transportability from multiple environments with limited experiments: Completeness results. page 280–288, 2014. URL <https://perma.cc/CF7C-MM7X>

⁷ **Transportability**

⁸ For me(KM) this resonated with a **Precautionary Principle** strategy of trying to reduce danger to Flora and Fauna (including us) and **Environments**.

⁹ ...On the usage of the description ‘**Transportability**’ here: let’s say we have some causal mechanistic knowledge from several heterogeneous systems that are parallels to or related to the system of interest where we only have very limited observations/data ... We do speculative causal reasoning with what we have, drawing parallels. I hope this helps,

¹⁰ David Penny. Charles darwin as a theoretical biologist in the mechanistic tradition. 1(1):e1–e1. ISSN 2036-265X. DOI: 10.4081/eb.2009.e1. URL <https://www.pagepress.org/journals/index.php/eb/article/view/eb.2009.e1>. Number: 1

a situation, we can argue that this Theory can move to an emerging truth, e.g., Darwin's Survival of the Fittest.

- Of course this framework is available for your critique, adaptations, re-design. My hope is *your analysis*¹¹ will include suggestions on how to investigate the below Health Disparity Borders with or not with this suggestion for a causal framework, adapt as you wish.
- Hill's view-points / criteria, includes dose-response observations and consistency of the observations, (See slide 11 in this show, https://bit.ly/Inquiry_A_Review)
- Speculative causal diagramming, (See slide 13), and thinking with the <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013> data:
 - Modifiable Risk Factors, LifeStyle Choices: Exercise, Eat Plants, Social and Psychological support ->
 - Longer Telomeres ->
 - Health of the Immune System: our objective is to maintain an uncompromised Immune System across a lifetime. See Reference 23 in <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013>: Damjanovic et al. 'Accelerated Telomere Erosion Is Associated with a Declining Immune Function of Caregivers of Alzheimer's Disease Patients.' Journal of Immunology vol. 179, no. 6, 15 Sept. 2007, p. 4249. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2262924/> ... I am not proposing you read the paper, please read the Abstract, and see if you can visualize the Telomere shortening in Figure 3. There is a section in the paper on Figure 3. titled: 'Caregivers of AD patients have significantly shorter telomere length of PBMC than controls' on page 5. The majority of primary caregivers of people with AD are relatives.
- I also propose that understanding molecular interactions guides our interpretation of a dose-response curve, a biological gradient. Consider this example for in vitro endpoints for asbestos toxicity including the generation of oxidative stress which results in DNA damage. DNA Damage at low levels, while measurable *in vitro*, is removed *in vivo* via cellular apoptosis - cells die, which is a much better health outcome than having staying around damaged DNA. Apoptosis represents an adaptive response and a threshold effect. Responses at low levels may not be indicative of disease outcomes, but rather of adaptive responses that indicate a threshold for disease observation, observing the biological gradient, a dose-response, causality: asbestos exposure ->oxidative stress->DNA damage.

¹¹ My reference to *your analysis* is referring to including in your response to the assignment a section(s) on developing theories on why and how the border exists, those theories guiding data collection. **Assignment:** Why do you think a Health Disparity Border exists and how would you investigate it?

Figure 2: I would argue that 'why' is a little different from 'what', I am asking you to respond with your take on 'why' is this happening, if you include 'what' or just do 'what' that is also acceptable. I liked the above representation because it has 'why' drifting into 'what'. We are going for 'why'. Please try to do 'Why, Compared to What',

Figure 3: I hope this helps with thinking about addressing 'why' with a Hypothesis/Theory. My Blue Arrow is about the flow of generating a Theory out of the collected data. My one Green Arrow is about using a Theory to guide the collection of (new) data. Think about the importance of a Scientific Imagination with this narrative flow for Causal Reasoning.

- One of my hopes for this course is we are developing *Critical Thinking*, into this conversation I would put in a *how to* on updating our theories based on information, new information, newly unearthed information, formerly hidden information, formerly differently construed information. I see this as part of the lineage of Darwin. Some of my colleagues (in Product Liability) believe and hold it is updating our theories by a specific amount based on evidence strength. This is effectively a reference to the work of Thomas Bayes.¹² For classroom teaching, I have found the latter to be less seductive to the class members. I share as: gradually getting better theories by constantly updating in proportion to the weight of the evidence and being ready for the acceptance of falsification evidence. (Darwin, Popper, Bayes) I support a collaboration with the theorist Toni Morrison for looking with subjectivity revealed. A way of running this is to consider the survival of our theories are guided by our learning of adequate and acceptable new evidence. The core logic in science is testing our ideas with new evidence; I argue that this is science literacy,
- I place Darwin as our ally prompting us to test our theories/ideas with new evidence; I argue that this is science literacy. I run Darwin's core insight on scientific analysis with Toni Morrison's directions to observe with her 'bowl' theory in mind. The year before she was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature Toni Morrison (TM) published *Playing in the Dark: Whiteness and the Literary Imagination, (1992)* in which she argued that the 'seminal works' of American literature are informed by their authors' determination to define themselves and their fellow white world against the *Black 'other'*. TM maintained that the suppression of this analysis made it difficult to perceive *race* as a vitally important context. TM framed this beautifully, it was as if she had been looking at the contents of a *fishbowl*, 'and suddenly I saw the bowl, the structure that transparently (and invisibly) permits the ordered life it contains to exist in the larger world'.¹³ TM urges us to look at the 'bowl'. For this Assignment I propose you use the 'bowl(s) theory to develop speculative analysis and writing on the exposures and outcomes.¹⁴ Can the 'bowl' be seen and what is seen? Can we look with a version of the Charles Darwin¹⁵ approach: using the 'bowl(s) theory to guide what to look for. The jarring outcomes of *Health Disparities* attached to *race* may provide a pathway to examining the 'bowl(s) or using the 'bowl(s) to look with greater acuity for correlates to Health. Speculating that the 'bowl' is real and a material force¹⁶, raises the *question* is it a presence in the production of *Health Disparities*. These questions will let us broaden the potential focus for the construction of ideas on *Health Disparities* and support us in entering the arena of *hypothetico-deductive analysis* built by Darwin, Bayes and Popper.¹⁷

¹² D. R. Bellhouse. The reverend thomas bayes, frs: A biography to celebrate the tercentenary of his birth. *Statistical Science*, 19(1), Feb 2004. ISSN 0883-4237. DOI: 10.1214/088342304000000189. URL <https://bit.ly/2ZhMKiT>

¹³ Toni Morrison. *Playing in the dark: Whiteness and the literary imagination*. 1992

¹⁴ **You can reject this theory of course, and come up with a theory to use for your collection and analysis of exposures and outcome.**

¹⁵ Darwin advised us to use our theories to guide our choosing of data to collect, and on designing adequate causal questions. He said something along the lines of 'If you don't have a theory you might just as well count the stones on Brighton beach.' circa 1861. See, Penny, David. *Charles Darwin as a Theoretical Biologist in the Mechanistic Tradition.* *Trends in Evolutionary Biology*, vol. 1, no. 1, Sept. 2009, <https://www.pagepress.org/journals/index.php/eb/article/view/eb.2009.e1>

¹⁶ To see an attempt to call on the 'bowl' please view Amy Cooper performing Racism, Central Park, NYC 2020, <https://youtu.be/iUQWd4q3tjA>

¹⁷ Please see Appendix 1. for the development of *causal reasoning* in my current teaching,

- Here I am raising TM's theory of the **'bowl'** as a guide for our collection of data in observational studies and the designing of causal questions. TM's theory also raises the issue of *health disparities* distributed on a racial gradient serving a greater ideological purpose. Traveling this path raises the issue are the *health disparities* as comforting as the literature TM critiques for some and dismaying, destructive to others.
- Speculating that the *'bowl'* is real and a material force raises a next step, that the *'bowl'* is a presence in the generation of **Health Disparities**. Is there evidence for the *'bowl'* creating and organizing the distribution of Health Disparities? Is there evidence for the *'bowl'* creating and organizing the distribution of Air Pollution?¹⁸ ***I(KM) am suggesting that this is a Theory that can guide the formation of adequate causal questions; this is me(KM) speculating, it does not have to be part of your analysis. It is an attempt to both 'Zoom in' and 'Zoom out' with how we are focusing on issues.*** Adequate causal questions let's us broaden the potential focus points for the construction of causal reasoning frameworks using Hill's viewpoints / criteria, causal inference, and speculative causal diagramming for *Health Disparities* and their borders. Can we investigate the *Health Disparities* with the theory provided by Toni Morrison's *'bowl'* in mind? **Does it help us ask adequate causal questions, and collect data? Are there other theories to help us ask adequate causal questions, and collect data? Is Darwin's analysis of without a theory / might as well 'count stones on Brighton Beach,' UK a good marker for us?**
- Please spend a little time thinking about the above description of **looking for the correlates and transportability**, and consider this data,
- I have curated two sets of data visuals that will hopefully aid us in considering **exposures, outcomes, causes, transportability and Why Does Place Matter**. I have placed the data visuals in the section titled **'Health Disparity Borders'**. Consider the below identified **#CoIncidence** of Asthma Hospitalizations¹⁹ and COVID-19 Disease-related Deaths. At the end of the Spring Semester 2020, this course raised the role of **Compromised Immune Systems** in the progress of a **#SarsCoV2 Infection to COVID-19 Disease**.
- My hope is we can develop together a working framework for our version of establishing causation. Below I present a work in progress on this, please consider joining the conversation; we are using Perusal for sharing annotations to the article you are currently reading.

¹⁸ Please see the Tessum et al results commentary on Air Pollution. See page 1 of 6 of the Tessum et al paper, top of second column, first paragraph. And see Harriet Washington's Chapter 3 of her book, *A Terrible Thing to Waste: Environmental Racism and Its Assault on the American Mind*.

Christopher W. Tessum, David A. Paoella, Sarah E. Chambliss, Joshua S. Apte, Jason D. Hill, and Julian D. Marshall. PM_{2.5} pollutants disproportionately and systematically affect people of color in the United States. 7(18):eabf4491. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abf4491. URL <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.abf4491>. Publisher: American Association for the Advancement of Science; and Harriet Washington. Chapter 3- poisoned world - the racial gradient of environmental neurotoxins. 2019. URL <https://www.hachettebookgroup.com/titles/harriet-a-washington/a-terrible-thing-to-waste/9780316509428/>

¹⁹ I became aware of the Asthma Hospitalizations **Health Disparity Border** running along East 96th Street while teaching at a school on East 96th between First and Second Avenue, *Life Sciences Secondary School (LSSS)*, 2016 - 2017.

A Very Selective Collection of Other Literature - Thinking Causal Framework

- Here is my attempt to describe a very selective collection of other literature in this field:
- The presence of the co-morbidities, e.g., obesity,²⁰ hypertension and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease increases the risk of developing severe COVID-19 Disease is established. Age is the strongest risk factor for severe COVID-19 outcomes, people with these underlying medical conditions are also at higher risk. Higher numbers of underlying conditions a person has, the higher the risk for severe COVID-19 outcomes.²¹
- Age-ing and loss of *Naïve* CD8 T-Cells may be linked risk factors for Covid-19 Disease. See Rydzynski et al. 'Antigen-Specific Adaptive Immunity to SARS-CoV-2 in Acute COVID-19 and Associations with Age and Disease Severity.' *Cell*, vol. 183, no. 4, Nov. 2020, pp. 996-1012.e19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.09.038>.²² and see our shared analysis on Pasqualino and the video recording on [Compromised Immune Systems](#).²³ The relation of COVID-19 Disease with Asthma remains to be resolved. **In the Assignment we are analyzing a coinciding Health Disparity Border for COVID-19 Disease and Asthma-related hospitalizations. We are thinking about Asthma Hospitalization and COVID-19 Disease severity.**
- An April 2021 publication of a meta-analysis²⁴ assessing the association between Asthma and COVID-19 Disease identified that the results of analysis do not provide clear evidence of increased risk of COVID-19 Disease diagnosis, hospitalizations, severity, or mortality due to Asthma; this result includes adjustment for known potential **confounders**.²⁵ The result is also consistent with earlier reporting analysed by Martinez 2021:²⁶ *the consistency of the evidence suggests that we are in the face of a surprising paradox: how is it possible that a disease that is known to be associated with increased susceptibility to a wide variety of viruses (including coronaviruses) (Ref.) may decrease the severity of one of the most lethal respiratory viruses ever encountered by humanity?* Is this still a valid observation in the closing days of 2022? No, Other Narratives are emerging. One of your colleagues (**Francisca Onyinye Egede, Fall 2022**) raised that she disagreed with Martinez. In communication with Francisca I brought forward my position is (1) The Asthma cohort was/is super careful to reduce the likelihood of infection, (2) **See that border at East 96th Street I have highlighted and my Figure 2, page 8; Dear All please bring the Asthma Severity and COVID-19 Disease Severity coinciding Health Disparity Border to Figure**

²⁰ Kenneth C. Y. Wong and Hon-Cheong So. Uncovering clinical risk factors and prediction of severe COVID-19: A machine learning approach based on UK biobank data. page 2020.09.18.20197319. DOI: 10.1101/2020.09.18.20197319. URL <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.09.18.20197319v1>

²¹ CDC. Science brief: Evidence used to update the list of underlying medical conditions associated with higher risk for severe covid-19 (updated 15 June 2022). *Centers for Disease Control and Prevention*, Feb 2020. URL <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/science/science-briefs/underlying-evidence-table.html>

²² Carolyn Rydzynski Moderbacher, Sydney I. Ramirez, Jennifer M. Dan, Alba Griffoni, Kathryn M. Hastie, Daniela Weiskopf, Simon Belanger, Robert K. Abbott, Christina Kim, Jinyong Choi, Yu Kato, Eleanor G. Crotty, Cheryl Kim, Stephen A. Rawlings, Jose Mateus, Long Ping Victor Tse, April Frazier, Ralph Baric, Bjoern Peters, Jason Greenbaum, Erica Ollmann Saphire, Davey M. Smith, Alessandro Sette, and Shane Crotty. Antigen-specific adaptive immunity to SARS-CoV-2 in acute COVID-19 and associations with age and disease severity. 183(4):996–1012.e19. ISSN 0092-8674. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2020.09.038. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0092867420312356>

²³ Kevin Moses. A compromised immune system in the era of sars-cov-2. May 2020. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6620638. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/6620638>

²⁴ Paul D. Terry, R. Eric Heidele, and Rajiv Dhand. Asthma in adult patients with COVID-19. prevalence and risk of severe disease. 203(7):893–905. ISSN 1535-4970. DOI: 10.1164/rccm.202008-3266OC

²⁵ **If you do not know of an action(s) of a confounding factor(s) you might misinterpret an Outcome and Exposure.** Please see next page ... If U - on the next page - is a *confounding factor*, e.g., a causative factor of both the Outcome and Exposure, we have to control for U to observe the relationship between the Exposure and the Outcome. We therefore find naturally occurring situations or construct situations where the U 'back door' path to affecting both the Outcome and Exposure is blocked. This gives us the opportunity to check on ... Does the Exposure cause Outcome.

²⁶ Fernando D. Martinez. Asthma in the time of COVID-19. 203(7):785–786. ISSN 1073-449X. DOI: 10.1164/rccm.202102-0389ED. URL <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/full/10.1164/rccm.202102-0389ED>. Publisher: American Thoracic Society - AJRCCM

2. We need to understand that coinciding by investigation and when there are holes in the data, do speculative causal writing ...The thing I am trying to persuade you to do. I put Martinez 2021 in because I wanted to raise their usage of '*paradox*' ... My take is that Asthma Severity and COVID-19 Disease Severity are coinciding. I hoped you might think of Figure 2 and come up with causal theories, I believe Martinez 2021 is not on the right track with their usage of 'paradox'. I would like to see a population-level examination of telomere length, plotting a map that travels block by block, measuring telomere length erosion. I would ensure that our plots crossed the Health Disparities, Gradients, and Borders for Asthma Hospitalization and COVID-19 Hospitalization. See the maps on the page <http://bit.ly/SpeculativeWriting> or in the document you are reading now at page 24 - 26 of 43. A proposed biomarker of Persistent Asthma is telomere length, telomere erosion.

- I did a review of Asthma and Telomere Erosion at Google Scholar. I felt this article can be added to a Proposal, if you are working on your Lit Review Proposal:
 - Al-Battawi et al. 2025 '**Association of Traffic Volume and Leukocyte Telomere Length of Malaysian Populations Living in Urban and Rural Areas.**' Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology, vol. 7, pp. 635 - 643, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enceco.2025.03.007>. Accessed 2 Dec. 2025.
 - Highlights:
 - First evidence to measure LTL in Malaysia's urban and rural adults
 - High-traffic (KL) group had significantly shorter LTL than low-traffic (HL) group ...I (KM) interpret this as exposure to reactive oxygen species, emitted by petrol-burning vehicles, see Lee et al in #TheCircumstances, <https://bit.ly/TheCircumstances> eroding DNA, eroding Telomeres, see <https://bit.ly/DetailingOxidativeStress>. kmNOTE > My-Investigation > ...I have to update this page with description generated for Frank.
 - There is a strong inverse relationship between traffic volume and LTL
 - Individual covariates were negatively correlated with LTL
- Please keep these points in mind: (A) Ecological fallacy in epidemiology ...is the failure in reasoning that arises when an inference is made about an individual based on aggregate data from a group cohort/population. This runs in both directions. And (B) Consider confounding factors: poverty - socio-economic stress- , Stress of all sorts, Mental Health, Food Deserts,

quality of healthcare, healthcare access, availability of health insurance, population size, vaccination, governmental policies, etc. ...There is quite a list which also includes <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013>. For reference here is Martinez 2021 asserting a '*paradox*' ...https://www.evernote.com/l/AAdkw6saE6tJ8r49CcfGeM5Gt_EFXuNnr2s

- We are in the midst of an evolving story and need to track the research: below please consider Bloom et al and Shi et al.
- Bloom, Cullinan, and Wedzicha. '*Asthma phenotypes and covid-19 risk: A population based observational study*.' American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine, 205(1):36 - 45, Jan 2022. ISSN 1073-449X. doi: 10.1164/rccm.202107-1704OC. URL <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/full/10.1164/rccm.202107-1704OC>
- **Bloom et al., Conclusion:** 'More severe asthma was associated with more severe COVID-19 outcomes[.]'
- Shi, Pan, Vasileiou, Robertson, and Sheikh. '*Risk of serious covid-19 outcomes among adults with asthma in Scotland: a national incident cohort study*.' The Lancet Respiratory Medicine, 10(4):347 - 354, Apr 2022. ISSN 2213-2600. doi: 10.1016/S2213-2600(21)00543-9. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2213260021005439>
- **Shi et al., Conclusion:** 'Adults with asthma who have required two or more courses of oral corticosteroids in the previous 2 years or a hospital admission for asthma before March 1, 2020, are at increased risk of both COVID-19 hospitalization, ICU admission or Death.'
- For Google Scholar curated citations to Terry et al 2021 see '*Terry: Asthma in adult patients with COVID-19. prevalence... - Google Scholar*.' 28 Oct. 2021, https://www.scholar.google.com/scholar?cites=6616865767956558079&as_sdt=2005&scioldt=0,5&hl=en.
- Martinez 2021 is published in the same journal and is a review of Terry et al 2021. Martinez 2021 speculates it is possible that '*type 2 inflammation may interfere with the receptor system for SARS-CoV-2 (Ref.) and that therapy with inhaled corticosteroids may decrease susceptibility to COVID-19 (Ref.), but the issue is far from settled*.'

- Severe Asthma, Asthma Hospitalization is also being associated with increased risk of COVID-19 hospitalization by some of the research output.^{27 28 29 30} Our identified *coincidence* is asking us to consider causal frameworks for observed *disease severity*.

Investigation of Health Disparity Borders

- Please see page 32 of 40: Appendix 3. Interlude: A Narrative-to-Data Framework for Mapping the Environmental Determinants of Immune Vulnerability.

²⁷ Bloom, Cullinan, and Wedzicha. Asthma phenotypes and covid-19 risk: A population-based observational study. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 205(1):36 – 45, Jan 2022. ISSN 1073-449X. DOI: 10.1164/rccm.202107-1704OC. URL <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/full/10.1164/rccm.202107-1704OC>

²⁸ Bloom et al., Conclusion: ‘More severe asthma was associated with more severe COVID-19 outcomes[.]’

²⁹ Shi, Pan, Vasileiou, Robertson, and Sheikh. Risk of serious covid-19 outcomes among adults with asthma in scotland: a national incident cohort study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 10(4):347 – 354, Apr 2022. ISSN 2213-2600. DOI: 10.1016/S2213-2600(21)00543-9. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2213260021005439>

³⁰ Shi et al., Conclusion: ‘Adults with asthma who have required two or more courses of oral corticosteroids in the previous 2 years or a hospital admission for asthma before March 1, 2020, are at increased risk of both COVID-19 hospitalization and ICU admission or death.’

COVID-19 related Deaths

...by Zip Code Area. New York City, 2020

- The **border** paralleling East 96th street shown by the green arrow is for all five named parameters,
- There are several incidence borders on this map that show a transition. I chose to examine the **border** at the green arrow because I am familiar with the location, East 96th Street, from Fifth Avenue to First Avenue, LSSS between Second and First, *I taught Env. Sci. at LSSS 2016 - 2017, a startling good encounter.*
- Source of map: 'COVID-19: Data - NYC Health.' 21 Aug. 2020, www1.nyc.gov/site/doh/covid/covid-19-data.page.
- I have captured map images from the above link for data available 20210414, Deaths and Hospitalizations related to COVID-19 Disease are shown on this and the next pages,

Asthma Hospitalizations

...by Zip Code Area. Children Aged 0-14. New York City, 2000

- Garg et al., 2000, Asthma Hospitalization range: lightest colouration is 0-1.99 per 1000, darkest pink is 7.91 - 17.55 per 1000.³¹
- There is a selection of recent citations to Garg et al, I am presenting Levene et al. 'The ongoing impact of COVID-19 on Asthma and pediatric emergency health-seeking behavior in the Bronx, an epicenter.' Am. J. Emerg. Med., vol. 43, 1 May. 2021, pp. 109-14. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0735675721000759>³²
 - Background: **The Bronx has the highest prevalence of Asthma in the United States (US), and was also an early COVID-19 epicenter.** World-wide reports describe significant declines in the pediatric emergency department (PED) visits during COVID-19. The ongoing impact of COVID-19 on all PED presentations, including Asthma, at an early epicenter is being studied beyond the pandemic peak and into the phases of locality re-opening. (I have slightly re-cast the Background by these authors.)
 - Conclusion: The pandemic cohort experienced a substantial decrease in the pediatric emergency department (PED) volume, but an increase in severity and admission rates, which was sustained through the NYS phase-II re-opening. Despite being located in an Asthma hub, the incidence of Asthma-related PED visits declined appreciably in the pandemic cohort. Future studies examining the effects of indoor allergens in isolation on pediatric Asthma are warranted.
 - Please analyze this with me: I (KM) can reconcile this data as the reticence of the Pandemic Cohort to approach an ER facility resulting in only absolute emergencies instigating an ER visit, a higher percentage of these visitors will need admission. **The behavioural response to the COVID-19 Disease era may also result in greater vigilance, social distancing, greater care towards potential indoor, outdoor allergens by the actions of a self-aware at risk Asthmatic community, includes some of my friends.**

³¹ Garg R., Karpati A., Leighton J., Perrin M., and Shah M. Asthma facts, second edition. New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene. page 50. URL <https://www.nyc.gov/assets/doh/downloads/pdf/asthma/facts.pdf>

³² Rachel Levene, Daniel M. Fein, Ellen J. Silver, Joanna R. Joels, and Hnin Khine. The ongoing impact of COVID-19 on asthma and pediatric emergency health-seeking behavior in the Bronx, an epicenter. 43:109-114. ISSN 0735-6757. DOI: 10.1016/j.ajem.2021.01.072. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0735675721000759>

Place Matters

- A potential starting point for speculative theories is that #PlaceMatters. In this course I am calling the health status transitions, **Health Disparity Borders**. The green arrow in the graphics points to a **border**. I would like us

to focus on designing interventions. What investigations do we design to aid people, What is the aid we need?

- The objective here is to increase our understanding of the relationship between our Health and the Health of our Environments. ... **Why does Place Matter to Human Health?**

The Assignment Question

- **For the Assignment**³³ I would like you to consider the coincidence of *Health Disparities* at the **border** identified above, **why do you think a Health Disparity Border exists and how would you investigate it**, I hope you will address the following,
 - **What are the possible primary drivers of the Health Disparities**; if you wish to think in terms of exposures and outcomes, please do, remember it is your choice on how you want to think about this. It is so worth being conscious of the proximity of racial and pollution gradients;³⁴ and the accompanying formation of **Health Disparity Borders**.
 - **Sometimes when we don't have the data, we need to look around and interpret what's happening, what's happening for / to people, for / to environments.**³⁵ Some of you might like to do a literature review (Final Project) on: 'Asthma' AND 'Covid' - see this Google Scholar search, <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=gsb4o&q=%22Asthma%22%20and%20%22Covid%22&lookup=o&hl=en>.
 - It is also worth considering possible **confounding factors** at these health transition borders. Search this document for references to '**confound**'. **And see Figure 2 of the document you are currently reading.**
 - In the Google Scholar search above I used 'Asthma' and not 'Asthma Hospitalizations', please consider switching back and forth and reviewing the results for both. ***The data here is on Asthma Hospitalizations.***
 - A possible biomedical approach to investigating the *Health Disparities* can consider measuring Telomere Lengths, to build a picture of health status. To offer treatment, we must show how we can escape from the exposures and structures causing harm.
 - I have an Autumn 2020 **DeBriefing on Asthma Hospitalization and Telomere Length** in another course, <https://bit.ly/2Tyt97E>, you might be interested in checking it out.
 - **How would you go about investigating why Health Disparity Borders exist?**

³³ **Assignment: Why do you think a Health Disparity Bor- der exists and how would you investigate it?**

³⁴ Harriet Washington. Chapter 3- poisoned world - the racial gradient of environmental neurotoxins. 2019. URL <https://www.hachettebookgroup.com/titles/harriet-a-washington/a-terrible-thing-to-waste/9780316509428/>

³⁵ Speculative Writing: Our theories are also our guides for the how and which data to collect, See https://www.evernote.com/l/AAfCMWsl3PZHlBH8aim94BPrQADma_Qw2Yo.

- The relationship between Asthma Hospitalization and severity of COVID-19 Disease³⁶ is being studied - see my citing to Bloom et al., 2022 and Shit et al., 2022 in the paper you are reading now - We are trying to analyze it here. I am following the subject. COVID-19 Disease risk assessment data in the presence of pre-existing co-morbidities is vital.
- * The article ³⁷ titled *Risk factors for severity and mortality in adult COVID-19 inpatients in Wuhan* provides detail to inform risk assessment. Li et al identified the ‘prevalence of Asthma in patients with COVID-19 was 0.9 percent, markedly lower than that in the adult population of Wuhan.’
- * Butler et al. reason with this in their paper: *Prevalence of comorbid Asthma in COVID-19 patients*.³⁸ ending with: ‘There remains a need for larger, more detailed epidemiologic and mechanistic studies for clarification to what extent COVID-19 poses a risk to patients of defined Asthma severity.’ Butler et al citing to Li et al.
- * A citation to Butler et al. is Sunjaya et al. *Asthma and risk of infection, hospitalization, ICU admission and mortality from COVID-19: Systematic review and meta-analysis[.]*’ which has an informative [c]onclusion: ‘*The findings from this study suggest that the prevalence of people with Asthma among COVID-19 patients is similar to the global prevalence of Asthma. The overall findings here suggest that people with Asthma have a lower risk than those without Asthma for acquiring COVID-19 and have similar clinical outcomes.*’³⁹
- * The lower risk in this research might have an as yet to be determined biological and a behavioural component(s); the behavioural component is potentially greater vigilance - social distancing by the actions of a perceived at risk Asthmatic community, The line of research is in flux see for example Shi et al 2022.⁴⁰
- * This is not an examination of Asthma Hospitalizations⁴¹. **Our Assignment embraces is there a rise in Asthma Hospitalizations coinciding with the rise in #SarsCov2 infections, hospitalizations, disease severity, both associated with rises in Air Pollution.**^{42 43 44}
 - As described above, the behavioural response to the COVID-19 Disease era may result in greater reticence towards approaching emergency rooms (ERs) and / or greater vigilance, social distancing, greater care towards potential allergens by the actions of a self-perceived at risk Asthmatic community,
 - **Please analyze this with me: I (KM) can reconcile the data as**

³⁶ What is the relationship between Asthma Hospitalization and severity of COVID-19 Disease?

³⁷ Xiaochen Li, Shuyun Xu, Muqing Yu, Ke Wang, Yu Tao, Ying Zhou, Jing Shi, Min Zhou, Bo Wu, Zhenyu Yang, Cong Zhang, Junqing Yue, Zhiguo Zhang, Harald Renz, Xiansheng Liu, Jungang Xie, Min Xie, and Jianping Zhao. Risk factors for severity and mortality in adult COVID-19 inpatients in wuhan. 146(1):110–118. ISSN 0091-6749. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaci.2020.04.006. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7152876/>

³⁸ Marcus W. Butler, Aoife O’Reilly, Eleanor M. Dunican, Patrick Mallon, Eoin R. Feeney, Michael P. Keane, and Cormac McCarthy. Prevalence of comorbid asthma in COVID-19 patients. 146(2):334–335. ISSN 0091-6749. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaci.2020.04.061. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7284278/>

³⁹ Anthony P. Sunjaya, Sabine M. Allida, Gian Luca Di Tanna, and Christine Jenkins. Asthma and risk of infection, hospitalization, ICU admission and mortality from COVID-19: Systematic review and meta-analysis. pages 1–14. ISSN 0277-0903. DOI: 10.1080/02770903.2021.1888116. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8022341/>

⁴⁰ Shi, Pan, Vasileiou, Robertson, and Sheikh. Risk of serious covid-19 outcomes among adults with asthma in scotland: a national incident cohort study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 10(4):347 – 354, Apr 2022. ISSN 2213-2600. DOI: 10.1016/S2213-2600(21)00543-9. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2213260021005439>

⁴¹ Garg R., Karpati A., Leighton J., Perrin M., and Shah M. *Asthma facts, second edition. new york city department of health and mental hygiene.* page 50. URL <https://www1.nyc.gov/assets/doh/downloads/pdf/asthma/facts.pdf>

⁴² Mario Coccia. Factors determining the diffusion of COVID-19 and suggested strategy to prevent future accelerated viral infectivity similar to COVID. 729:138474. ISSN 0048-9697. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138474. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7169901/>

⁴³ Timo Mathys, Fábio Teodoro de Souza, Demian da Silveira Barcellos, and Ingrid Molderez. The relationship among air pollution, meteorological factors and

the reticence of the Pandemic Cohort to approach an ER facility resulting in only absolute emergencies instigating an ER visit, a higher percentage of these visitors will need admission.

- Declines in Asthma Hospitalizations may be indicators for the above behaviour,⁴⁵
- * This still leaves the Health Disparity Borders open for your speculative writing,

Our Time Together

- I am treating **our time together** as an opportunity to report on significant Public Health issues, and their relationship to place,

Searching for Causation

- The identified **borders** are significant Public Health issues and exploring relationships to places, environments, exposures is a valid investigation. **What are the conditions of the lives across that border**, what are the modifiable risk factors across that **border**, it might get us to health interventions,⁴⁶

• Why the #CoIncidence,

- There are a range of preliminary questions, Why does Place matter,
- What other health issues coincide at this **border**,
- **Consider, e.g., a putative theory / hypothesis could explain that populations exposed to chronic air pollution are associated with a COVID-19 Disease incidence in line with chronic DNA injury, DNA sequence changes, telomere shortening,**
- If you, we are thinking about dangerous fortune, reference 23 of <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013> resonates with the heartbreaking COVID-19 deaths amongst caregivers, resonates with a compromised Immune System,
 - Reference 23: Damjanovic et al. ‘Accelerated Telomere Erosion Is Associated with a Declining Immune Function of Caregivers of Alzheimer’s Disease Patients.’ ...I recommended at a minimum read the Abstract please, ⁴⁷
 - I was hoping that highlighting Damjanovic et al ([Gotlib et al](#), [Lee et al](#) and [Chae et al](#)) would help you consider some groups⁴⁸ should be the recipients of public health initiatives, e.g., [have their telomeres](#)

⁴⁵ Rachel Levene, Daniel M. Fein, Ellen J. Silver, Joanna R. Joels, and Hnin Khine. The ongoing impact of COVID-19 on asthma and pediatric emergency health-seeking behavior in the bronx, an epicenter. 43:109–114. ISSN 0735-6757. DOI: 10.1016/j.ajem.2021.01.072. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0735675721000759>

⁴⁶ Dean Ornish, Jue Lin, June M Chan, Elissa Epel, Colleen Kemp, Gerdi Weidner, Ruth Marlin, Steven J Frenda, Mark Jesus M Magbanua, Jennifer Daubenmier, and et al. *Effect of comprehensive lifestyle changes on telomerase activity and telomere length in men with biopsy-proven low-risk prostate cancer: 5-year follow-up of a descriptive pilot study. The Lancet Oncology*, 14(11): 1112–1120, Oct 2013. ISSN 1470-2045. DOI: 10.1016/S1470-2045(13)70366-8. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1470204513703668>

⁴⁷ Think on the Care of the Caregivers,

⁴⁸ Amanda K. Damjanovic, Yinhua Yang, Ronald Glaser, Janice K. Kiecolt-Glaser, Huy Nguyen, Bryon Laskowski, Yixiao Zou, David Q. Beversdorf, and Nan-ping Weng. Accelerated telomere erosion is associated with a declining immune function of caregivers of alzheimer’s disease patients. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md. : 1950)*, 179(6):4249–4254, Sep 2007. ISSN 0022-1767. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1860606/>

measured, inviting them to participate in O et al. type interventions, Save People,

- On O et al., ...they do not have a Causal step as in ...smoking-related lung cancers: **Benzopyrene** a component of tobacco smoke can intercalate into a DNA chain changing the DNA sequence, with potentially disastrous consequences moving a cell from Normal to AbNormal to Cancerous if left un-repaired and the cell is not killed by the Immune System, a **disastrous flow**. This is the beginning of putting together a direct Causal step (Benzopyrene intercalating ...). **O et al., do not have that type of Causal step but they do have a unidirectional dose-response, ...some of the participants maintained, lengthened telomeres.** The O et al team have a **dose-response** - identifying⁴⁹ on where to look for those causal steps. Here are citations to O et al, https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed?linkname=pubmed_pubmed_citedin&from_uid=24051140. I used the citations to check if the work of O et al had been refuted or had it received reproducibility checks, had it been supported: Yes on supported. The O et al specific lifestyle changes that lengthened telomeres are identified as showing a dose-response relationship, I would argue this is **a critical observation**, and beyond a showing of associated variables. You are free to argue this any way you wish and please extend our reading for the Assignment into a review of at least the introduction of this paper, Hernán, Miguel A. ***'The C-Word: Scientific Euphemisms Do Not Improve Causal Inference From Observational Data.'***⁵⁰ And why it matters most: **we need tools for eliminating the inequalities in health.**

Causal Reasoning

- **Generating information that can be translated into effective preventive or treatment strategies for the disparities in health is the way to go,**
- There is a need to distinguish the **adequate causal question** from the *investigatory steps* used to answer it.⁵¹ Don't get misled on the procedure used by O et al, sure it is not a vast study group but they have stunning, reproducible observational data: **lengthening telomeres** that resonates with their initiating investigatory steps, their **adequate causal questions**,⁵²
 - * Chae et al observed lengthened telomeres emerging from an encounter with racism by a pro-Black sense of self and others; I am calling this the therapy of **self-love**.⁵³ I argue all five papers, Chae et al, Damjonovic et al, Gotlib et al, Lee et al, O et al, inspire **causal reasoning**.

⁴⁹ Speculative Design ...I(KM) hope

we can discuss what methods are most likely to deliver causal evidence on the social and environmental determinants of health. See our slide show http://bitly.com/LivesToLive_HLE for more on the social and environmental determinants, ...**the Assignment might need your speculative reasoning, writing**

⁵⁰ Miguel A. Hernán. The c-word: Scientific euphemisms do not improve causal inference from observational data. *American Journal of Public Health*, 108(5):616, May 2018. DOI: 10.2105/AJPH.2018.304337. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5888052/>

⁵¹ Our starting position is speculative writing on the root causes, ...Will we subsequently find the *Disparities* sourced here,

⁵² <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013>

⁵³ One of the futures I hope for AI is a role in building peoples concept of their own self worth, a conversation companion,

- * I(KM) am trying to open up opportunities for current and future theory generation in observational studies and the identification of potential new targets for screening and precautionary policies founded in the *Precautionary Principle ... going for identifying the conditions of our lives* that lead to Compromised Immune Systems,
- * What are critical observations, I am arguing a dose-response observation of lengthening telomeres, that is reproducible, ...gets me/us to we are looking at a causation story, we do not have causal steps, we are building a picture, [details](#),
- * This is the foundational work for telomere length: The Nobel Prize ⁵⁴ in Physiology or Medicine 2009. www.nobelprize.org/prizes/medicine/2009/illustrated-information. Identifying a telomere, the enzyme telomerase and their roles,
- * There is work trying to reach the causal steps of telomere shortening, consider reviewing Oxidative Stress bit.ly/DeBriefing_Resources_Dose_Response ... maybe good Literature Review material for a Final Project,

⁵⁴ [The Nobel Prize](#)

Causal Question

- Here are four points I think we should consider for **working with a Theory**,⁵⁵
 - *Can we develop a theory, **adequate Causal Question(s) (Darwin)**,⁵⁶ does the question help us in designing methods for our study, collecting data,*
 - We need a theory to guide the collection of data,
 - Can we reach a causal analysis with our study? ...the adequate causal question(s) should hover above us during **the Assignment**,
 - Fourth, **I hope we are choosing an ecological approach**; e.g., ‘there are suggestions that certain populations, such as South Asian groups, may develop metabolic syndrome and diabetes at lower levels of obesity as assessed by BMI than other populations such as Caucasians.’ ...taken from reflections posted by Basu et al., “*The Relationship of Sugar to Population-Level Diabetes Prevalence: An Econometric Analysis of Repeated Cross-Sectional Data*.”⁵⁷ For me too, the basic tenets of an ecological approach are true: outcomes in their environments are the phenomena to be explained.⁵⁸ ⁵⁹

⁵⁵ [Working with a Theory](#)

⁵⁶ [Try to draw a real simple diagram illustrating the question,](#)

⁵⁷ Sanjay Basu, Paula Yoffe, Nancy Hills, and Robert H. Lustig. The relationship of sugar to population-level diabetes prevalence: An econometric analysis of repeated cross-sectional data. 8(2):e57873. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0057873. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0057873>

⁵⁸ Karen E. Adolph. An ecological approach to learning in (not and) development. 63(3):180–201. ISSN 0018-716X, 1423-0054. DOI: 10.1159/000503823. URL <https://www.karger.com/Article/FullText/503823>. Publisher: Karger Publishers

⁵⁹ **Be Aware:** Ecological fallacy in epidemiology is the failure in reasoning that arises when an inference is made about an individual based on aggregate data from a group. We are not making that mistake.

Overweight and COVID-19 Disease Vulnerabilities

- I thought the following great work on the relationship of being overweight / obese and risks of COVID-19 Disease [...] ‘Results: A total of 1191 severe and 358 fatal [COVID-19 Disease] cases were identified. [...] Since only pre-diagnostic clinical data were available, the main objective of this analysis was to identify baseline risk factors. [...] For the prediction of mortality, the top features were age, systolic blood pressure, waist circumference (WC), urea and [waist-hip ratio(WHR)]’ Wong and So. *Uncovering clinical risk factors and prediction of severe COVID-19: A machine learning approach based on UK Biobank data.*⁶⁰
- **Are we losing the vulnerable because we do not know enough about variations in vulnerability, would measuring telomeres help our knowledge?**
 - Of course, ‘environmental factors such as sugar consumption should be investigated as potential factors in this interaction.’ Basu et al.,
 - We are looking for the patterns of *health disparities* for different diseases, e.g., **do we see that some diseases have the same pattern of health disparities?** Is it Place?
 - This observation would suggest investigating the social and environmental determinants of health if we see the same Health Disparity Borders for disease x, disease y and disease ...

⁶⁰ Kenneth C. Y. Wong and Hon-Cheong So. Uncovering clinical risk factors and prediction of severe COVID-19: A machine learning approach based on UK biobank data. page 2020.09.18.20197319. DOI: 10.1101/2020.09.18.20197319. URL <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.09.18.20197319v1>

Our Course

- In our course, we are trying to reach an understanding that prevention is *dependent on the development and application of exposure and outcome observations*,⁶¹ *we might not get to experiment for a range of health and ethical concerns. We can of course spend our energies looking for Fortuitous Randomisation arising without our intervention in the World around us. Fortuitous Randomisation, is e.g., finding a community living adjacent to a pesticide production plant and finding a similar community not living adjacent to a pesticide production plant. E.g., finding a community living with access to a Mediterranean Diet and finding a similar community living with no access to a Mediterranean Diet. We would look into the World for situations where we speculate there is a causal pathway to an outcome we have observed, all other pathways not being there, or canceled out. See https://bit.ly/CausalAnalysis_History.*
- Think of the **Health Disparity Border** identified above, approximately at East 96th street, I would be willing to argue the disparities at that border

⁶¹ **Exposure and outcome observations,**

are an emergency and intervention requires us to ... ?

- Measure telomere lengths on both sides of the Health Disparity Border is a start,
- Our attempts to develop Causal Reasoning: included *Hill's*⁶² contribution to *Causal Inference*, the embracing of a hypothetico-deductive reasoning approach distilled from Charles Darwin, Thomas Bayes, Karl Popper, see our slide show https://bit.ly/Inquiry_A_Review, the DeBriefing for Pasqualino, <https://www.evernote.com/l/AAdQaINJ8GtHTqQeXtOXZLbxNjDDwhFk9gA> and the surfacing up of fragments, notions of mechanistic causal knowledge/research,
 - In this show we do an analysis of supporting a *Correlation* type statement but maintain the objectives of a causal analysis, see Assignment_#1 Fall 2020,
- *Assignment_#1* - Telomere Length, *Is there a causation story*,⁶³ is also trying to highlight the need for prevention strategies in human health, http://bit.ly/Assignment_1_20200824. The theme of Assignment_#1 was continued in a 2020 Assignment, http://bit.ly/Assignment_2_Autumn2020, Question (a) Is measuring Telomere Length a means to identify vulnerable populations? Discuss, Question (b) If the conditions of our lives are a collection of Modifiable Risk Factors, possibly affecting individual or/and group experienced Environments, please design the public health interventions to identify and help populations⁶⁴ including an identification of any Modifiable Risk Factors of concern? Discuss,
 - I have printed a DeBriefing on the meaning of Telomere Length and made it part of this combined PDF, see the next page,
 - See also the *assignment on*: https://bit.ly/Pasqualino_SurvivorStories and a PreBriefing here, check out the Loom videos, <bit.ly/PreBriefingPasqualino>, this is us beginning our story of Biological Age-ing, telomere shortening and a Compromised Immune System,

⁶² Sir Austin Bradford Hill. The environment and disease: association or causation? *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 108(1): 32, Jan 2015. DOI: 10.1177/0141076814562718. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4291332/>

⁶³ *Is there a causation story*,

⁶⁴ I(KM) came across this excellent vehicle for health messaging: Treanor & Nunis 'Why Africa's animation scene is booming,' BBC World Service, 14 Oct. 2020, www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-54438334. My thoughts went to health messaging, healthy eating,

Thank you for all your submissions, reading this,
K Moses JD PhD

Other Notes: an Assignment DeBriefing on Telomere Length and Modifiable Risk Factors,

- **Here is an excerpt from the DeBriefing:**
 - * Consider this, can telomere length lead us to better public health interventions. While public interest for interventions exists, the language used is often interpreted as curtailing, e.g., in the USA particular constructions of freedom intervene and cast government initiatives as interference in 'private' choices for one's life. Such narratives undermine the acceptability of gov. interventions to protect population health. Would knowledge of shorter telomeres make it easier to reach narratives for health as a Human Right, can we then reach *processed food reformulations*,⁶⁵ regulate advertising and promotions, fruits and vegetable subsidies, higher taxation of tobacco, alcohol and highly processed foods ...please consult the WHO's *'best buys'* for preventing noncommunicable diseases (NCDs),⁶⁶

Behavioural Change

- **Do you think knowledge of Telomere Length might provide people with better reassurance for adjusting to, for in many cases, drastic Lifestyle changes?**⁶⁷ And it might be just about raising health literacy, giving people the opportunity for more health knowledge. How can we persuade the vulnerable to buy into our health recommendations, and avoid highly processed foods? **Is it really the case that highly processed foods are out-competing fruit and vegetables on price?** How can we get those who need it the most to The Precautionary Principle, <http://bit.ly/PrecautionaryP?>⁶⁸ Sharing information on Telomere Length is possibly an introductory step to making lifestyle changes. In an era of assessing sustainability, the impact of consumption on the status of planet Earth is very relevant to lifestyle choices made. **What interventions can transform our realities? How do we enrich learning outcomes,**
- A public health community initiative will need to move to the underlying cultural, social, political nature of the issues, including the conditions of our lives. A smart approach would use language embracing *local communities*, framing the issues as *our health, our longevity*, showing proposed solutions concerning, e.g., taxes on sugary beverages and regulation going to healthy levels of salt and trans fats in

⁶⁵ **Reformulating Processed Foods,**

⁶⁶ **World Health Organization.** Tackling NCDs: 'best buys' and other recommended interventions for the prevention and control of noncommunicable diseases. (WHO/NMH/NVI/17.9), 2017. URL <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/259232>. Accepted: 2017-10-12T15:09:59Z

⁶⁷ Oliver T. Mytton, Emma Boyland, Jean Adams, Brendan Collins, Martin O'Connell, Simon J. Russell, Kate Smith, Rebekah Stroud, Russell M. Viner, and Linda J. Cobiac. **The potential health impact of restricting less-healthy food and beverage advertising on UK television between 05.30 and 21.00 hours: A modelling study.** *PLOS Medicine*, 17(10): e1003212, Oct 2020. ISSN 1549-1676. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1003212. URL <https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.1003212>

⁶⁸ **Do you think knowledge of Telomere Length might provide people with a better incentive for adjusting to Lifestyle changes? What is seductive knowledge?**

highly processed foods. We must build counter-narratives to guide us to health,

This dig. is hosted here:
https://bit.ly/CausalTeachingNotes_UXY
 - Latest Update to pink notes is here:

- If you do not know of the U(s) you might misinterpret an Outcome and Exposure relationship for X and Y,
- U is a confounder, a causative factor of both X and Y. If we can control for the U(s), e.g., we block the 'back door' path of causing a change/increase in X and Y if U changes/increases. This allows us to check on Does X affect Y?
- My diagram is hopefully an evolution of a 'back door' theory by and diagram at '(a) Model 1' presented by Cinelli et al. 'A Crash Course in Good and Bad Controls'. SSRN Electronic Journal, Mar. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3689437> ... The Judea Pearl Group. We are also interested in the addition of notions on a biological mechanism. We have to pull in many sources of information to our analysis, so yes we are in the field observational analysis and embrace potential biological mechanisms including the interests of this course> Oxidative Stress and DNA Damage. A Scientific Imagination is critical to this approach, I am calling it Imaginative Reasoning,
- This diagram helps me (KM) to think of possible confounding factors (e.g., U(s)), exposures (X) and outcomes (Y) in the environments we are studying. The Assignment, <https://bit.ly/TheCircumstances> is hopefully helping us to think about environments that are a collection of modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors ... The Totality of the Environment(s).
- On the analysis of confounding factors and bias I recommend we think about using negative and positive controls for detection of said in our observational studies, see Bowe et al. 'Acute and Postacute Sequelae Associated with SARS-CoV-2 Reinfection.' Nature Medicine, vol. 28, no. 11. 2022. pp. 2398 - 405. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-02051-3>

Figure 4: My (KM) Causal Teaching Notes: Thinking about Confounding Factors ...poverty, quality of healthcare, availability of health insurance, population size, vaccination, governmental policies, food deserts, discrimination, ...

Source: "COVID-19: Data Main - NYC Health." 21 Aug. 2020, www1.nyc.gov/site/doh/covid/covid-19-data.page.

COVID-19 Data by ZIP Code

- Case rate
- Death rate
- Percent positive tests
- Case count
- Death count

Death Count

- 10
- 50
- 100

Marking East 96th St.

Figure 5: The map provides confirmed death counts with a positive result since March 2020, NYC.Gov,

[Death Count, COVID-19 Data, NYC Health 20210414](#)

Hospitalizations Deaths

Deaths per 100,000 people

Figure 6: The map provides death rates with a positive result over 28 days. To accommodate standard reporting delays for hospitalization and death data, these are published at a 14-day lag. Accessed 20210414,

Hospitalizations, COVID-19 Data, NYC Health 20210414

Hospitalizations Deaths

Hospitalizations per 100,000 people

Figure 7: The map provides hospitalization

FIGURE 17

Asthma Hospitalization Rates by ZIP Code Area, Children Aged 0-14, New York City, 2000

SOURCE: Garg R, Karpati A, Leighton J, Perrin M, Shah M. "Asthma Facts," Second Edition.

New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene, May 2003., See, <https://www1.nyc.gov/assets/doh/downloads/pdf/asthma/facts.pdf>

* As of 2020 this circa 2000 data set is still being cited, see https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=16553491187225212129&hl=en&as_sdt=2005&sciodt=0.5

* And me (KM) teaching Autumn 2020: Moses, K. Handout_20201008: Assignment #4, Saving Lives, Speculative Writing On #theCoincidence of #Asthma Hospitalizations and #COVID-19 Disease, ... Ongoing Reflections on #Sars-CoV-2, A Compromised Immune System and Risk Assessment. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4107132>

Figure 8: This Figure is from NYC.Gov, "Asthma Facts," May 2003.

- How are we going to persuade people who are eating highly processed foods to demand less salt and less trans fats?
What can we learn about addressing the social and environmental determinants of health? Is Telomere Length a way of bringing people to a consideration of their long term health,⁶⁹
- There are some observations in the field that say **precaution now**. *There are stories for a correlation between 'nuchal (neck) subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT) thickness, a surrogate marker of central trunk-weighted obesity,' [as an independent predictor of shortening Telomere Length,]*⁷⁰

Speculative Design and Writing

- A **speculative concept** is shorter telomeres are part of a causation story leading to a Compromised Immune System,⁷¹ which may be, e.g., needed for understanding the relationship between obesity and the risk of COVID-19 Disease progressing, see bit.ly/DeBriefing_Resources_Dose_Response for a beginning of our analysis on the impact of Oxidative DNA Damage and Stress on the functioning of telomerase and telomeres.⁷² Reminder **telomerase** is the enzyme we are focusing on as the maintainer of telomere length.
- *I highly recommend Wong and So. 'Uncovering clinical risk factors and prediction of severe COVID-19: A machine learning approach based on UK Biobank data.'* medRxiv, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, 22 Sept. 2020, Preprint Server, <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.09.18.20197319v1>,
- Wong and So provide great work on obesity and COVID-19⁷³
...*'Results: A total of 1191 severe and 358 fatal [COVID-19] cases were identified. [] Since only pre-diagnostic clinical data were available, the main objective of this analysis was to identify baseline risk factors. [] For the prediction of mortality, the top features were age, systolic blood pressure, waist circumference (WC), urea and waist-hip ratio(WHR).'*
- I would put the above forward as a putative theory, there is a correlation between excessive weight gain and increased risk of the COVID-19 Acute Respiratory Syndrome progressing,
- *If this is the flow, **Theory**: being overweight, being obese promotes the development of shorter telomeres, leading to a compromised Immune System, creating a vulnerability to COVID-19 disease progressing, ...it might be precautionary to urge measurement of telomeres, show the*

Figure 9: Walk on by ...or demand change, **Is Telomere Length a way of bringing people to a consideration of their long term health,**

⁷⁰ Harald Mangge, Markus Herrmann, Gunter Almer, Sieglinde Zelzer, Reinhard Moeller, Renate Horejsi, and Wilfried Renner. Telomere shortening associates with elevated insulin and nuchal fat accumulation. *Scientific Reports*, 10(11):6863, Apr 2020. ISSN 2045-2322. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-63916-6. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-63916-6>

⁷¹ A **speculative concept** is shorter telomeres are part of a causation story leading to a Compromised Immune System,

⁷² A putative theory,

⁷³ Wong and So, 2020 is great work on obesity and COVID-19,

results, change diet, increase movement, urge weight loss.⁷⁴ It will mean giving people direct information about what they need to change, e.g., in their diet, which means surmounting cultural, social, political beliefs and tropes.

- Further, there is more support for a correlation showing prematurely shortened telomeres significantly associated with the rising risk of cancer mortality, see Shen et al, 2020.⁷⁵ And see, Kamrunnahar et al, 2020.⁷⁶ *Conclusions: Patients with ovarian cancer (OC) and cervical cancer (CC) with shorter lymphocyte telomeres have significantly reduced survival; therefore, the peripheral blood lymphocyte telomere length is a prognostic biomarker in OC and CC,*
- A **theory** is biological age-ing and/or shorter telomeres are part of a causation story to a Compromised Immune System,⁷⁷ which may be needed for understanding rising Cancer risk,
- **Being ready to speculatively design for investigating a range of Health Disparities and remedying the Disparities currently appears to be a good public health investigator approach,**
- **p.s. 'Measurable'** describes a biomedical attitude towards Telomere Length. Short Telomeres can be an outcome of injury, DNA damage, e.g., loss-of-function mutations in the genes encoding the telomerase enzyme complex that maintains and lengthens telomeres. You might be interested in reviewing Alder et al. 'Diagnostic utility of telomere length testing in a hospital-based setting.' PNAS USA. 2018;115(10): E2358 - E2365. <https://www.pnas.org/content/115/10/E2358>⁷⁸ ...Remember these papers have an Abstract, Introduction, and Conclusion, it may not be necessary to read the whole paper to get the information we need. If TL is measurable and an indicator of biological health, should we measure, think and can we intervene to save lives or at least more years,

⁷⁴ A Plant-Based Diet,

⁷⁵ G. Shen, J.-Y. Huang, Yu-Qing Huang, and YingQing Feng. The relationship between telomere length and cancer mortality: Data from the 1999–2002 national healthy and nutrition examination survey (NHANES). 24(1):9–15. ISSN 1760-4788. DOI: 10.1007/s12603-019-1265-z. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12603-019-1265-z>

⁷⁶ Kamrunnahar Shanta, Kentaro Nakayama, Masako Ishikawa, Tomoka Ishibashi, Hitomi Yamashita, Seiya Sato, Hiroki Sasamori, Kiyoka Sawada, Sonomi Kurose, Hossain Mohammad Mahmud, Sultana Razia, Kouji Iida, Noriyoshi Ishikawa, and Satoru Kyo. Prognostic value of peripheral blood lymphocyte telomere length in gynecologic malignant tumors. 12(6):1469. DOI: 10.3390/cancers12061469. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6694/12/6/1469>.

Number: 6 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute

⁷⁷ A **theory** is biological age-ing and/or shorter telomeres are part of a causation story to a Compromised Immune System,

⁷⁸ Jonathan K. Alder, Vidya Sagar Hanumanthu, Margaret A. Strong, Amy E. DeZern, Susan E. Stanley, Clifford M. Takemoto, Ludmila Danilova, Carolyn D. Applegate, Stephen G. Bolton, David W. Mohr, and et al. Diagnostic utility of telomere length testing in a hospital-based setting. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(10):E2358–E2365, Mar 2018. ISSN 0027-8424, 1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1720427115. URL <https://www.pnas.org/content/115/10/E2358>

Who is dying: COVID-19 related Deaths

...New York City, 2020, 2021

'Dear Colleague: COVID-19 Update,' Week of May 3-9, 2020

Figure 1. Age-adjusted rates of confirmed and probable COVID-19 deaths in New York City, by race and ethnicity, as of April 27, 2020.

Note: A death is classified as confirmed if the decedent was a NYC resident who had a positive SARS-CoV-2 laboratory test. A death is classified as probable if the decedent was a NYC resident who had no known positive laboratory test for SARS-CoV-2 but the death certificate lists as a cause of death "COVID-19" or an equivalent. Hispanic/Latino includes people of any race. People of other races are not shown

[Data from the New York City Health Department](#)

- For more research on who is dying here are some additional sources,
- Oppel, Richard A., Jr., et al. 'The Fullest Look Yet at the Racial Inequity of Coronavirus.' N.Y. Times, 5 July 2020, www.nytimes.com/interactive/2020/07/05/us/coronavirus-latinos-african-americans-cdc-data.html,
- Andrasfay and Goldman (2020). *Reductions in 2020 US life expectancy due to COVID-19 and the disproportionate impact on the Black and Latino populations*. MedRxiv, 2020.07.12.20148387. <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.07.12.20148387v3>
- See <https://bit.ly/TheCircumstances> and the PreBriefing page at https://bit.ly/PreBriefing_TheCircumstances, Saving Lives: Telomere Length and Modifiable Risk Factors,
- Post the disclosure of the LA County Council President Nury Martinez & Co. [recording](#),⁷⁹ I am supporting a transformation to the usage by the CDC, and other health reporting agencies of the identifier '**Hispanic/Latino**'. I interpret the 'Hispanic/Latino' construction in Public Health is a distraction from caring for the health of Asian, Black and Indigenous populations in the said construction such that the Health Data does not provide data for analysis of the Health of the populations

Figure 10: 'Dear Colleague: COVID-19 Update,' New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene, Week of May 3-9, 2020. <https://www1.nyc.gov/assets/doh/downloads/pdf/imm/covid-19-providers-dear-colleague-updates-05052020.pdf>.

Ringo H.W. Chiu/Associated Press

Figure 11: President Nury Martinez, LA County Council

⁷⁹ Julia Wick, Robert Meeks, Salvador Hernandez, Summer Lin, and J.R. Lizarraga. Breaking down crucial moments in the racist leaked recording of L.A. councilmembers. *Los Angeles Times*, Oct 2022. URL <https://lat.ms/3SQa5xK>

within the construction. The **recording** is about gerrymandering, money in brown paper bags, racism and anti-semitism; and how council members⁸⁰ stay in power. It resonates with reported discrimination data in a 2022 MMWR **report**: Padilla et al. ***'HIV Stigma and Health Care Discrimination Experienced by Hispanic or Latino Persons with HIV - United States***, 2018 - 2020. MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep 2022;71:1293 - 1300. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7141a1> **“What is added by this report?** *Hispanic persons with HIV commonly reported HIV stigma and health care discrimination. Among Hispanic persons with HIV, HIV stigma was highest among women (median stigma score equals 35.6 of 100) and American Indian or Alaska Native persons (median stigma score equals 32.7 of 100); health care discrimination was experienced more frequently by men than by women (23% vs. 18%) and by Black or African American Hispanic persons than by White Hispanic persons (28% vs. 21%).*⁸¹ *Efforts to detect Health Disparities issuing from discrimination are appropriate. Efforts to identify Asian, Black and Indigenous population members in the grouping ‘Hispanic/Latino’ are appropriate.*

⁸⁰ Kate Linthicum. Mexico’s new racial reckoning: A movement protests colorism and white privilege. *Los Angeles Times*, Oct 2022. URL <https://www.latimes.com/world-nation/story/2022-10-20/mexico-anti-racism-movement-protests-colorism>

⁸¹ Mabel Padilla. Hiv stigma and health care discrimination experienced by hispanic or latino persons with hiv — united states, 2018–2020. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 71, 2022. ISSN 0149-21951545-861X. DOI: 10.15585/mmwr.mm7141a1. URL <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/71/wr/mm7141a1.htm>

Assignment

Assignment: Why do you think a **Health Disparity Border** exists and how would you investigate it?

Support

I built this document with templates from (1) kjhealy. 'latex-custom-kjh.' GitHub, 21 Oct. 2020. Github, <https://github.com/kjhealy/latex-custom-kjh> and (2) the Tufte- \LaTeX document classes.

Appendices, Developing Theories and AutoGPT

Appendix 1. Developing Causal Reasoning

DeBriefing on Biological Ageing for the "Pasqualino Assignment", 20230426120816UTC_ [! \(KM\) am working on this here, https://bit.ly/MyNotes_Pasqualino](https://bit.ly/MyNotes_Pasqualino)

- *Can comprehensive lifestyle changes protect our Immune System from accelerated age-ing, this is a developing, evolving story, gotta Eat Plants, Reduce Stress, Run, Walk, etc.*
- *I also wanted to present to you a/my take on reaching **Causal Reasoning** with analysis of:*
 - **1. The role of Hill's 'view-points'** - including a choice to focus on **Dose-Responses and Reproducibility** of the observations in coming up with a theory, on a relationship of an exposure to an outcome,
 - **2. Hypothetico-Deductive Reasoning (Darwin, Popper)** with our theories and gathering of the new observations, data, evidence: we look for **Reproducibility (Consistency)** or the absence* of Reproducibility, the absence being a reason to doubt the validity of our theories, and re-design our theories. We are testing our theories/ideas with the new evidence,
 - * Many of our theories will be wrong, flawed and need re-design,
 - *Critical Thinking: The core logic in science is testing our ideas with new evidence; I argue that this is science literacy. I hope We can think of critical thinkers as being 'smart and do[ing] things that intelligent and observant people would do[.]' (Spoken by Jordan Peele 2017 on his film "Get Out", see <https://bit.ly/3MOMXCB> <Accessed 20220525>*
 - **3. Causal Reasoning ... thoughts on mechanisms,**
 - We need to have a notion(s), **fragments** of knowledge focused on an underlying mechanism, a molecular biological mechanism that resonates with our above observations. We bring up **mechanistic fragments** from our other knowledge, our other relevant knowledge can include new research or distant analogies,
 - I try to keep myself aware of the current research on **Oxidative Stress (OS) damage**. OS can damage DNA, proteins, carbohydrates and lipids (fats). Oxidants are highly reactive substances containing oxygen. These oxidants result from, e.g., infection, air pollution (PM2.5), alcohol, tobacco and Advanced Glycation End Products (AGEs or Glycotoxins, see <http://bit.ly/EatLotsOfPlants>), and Stress. Think of OS damage as injury that can accelerate telomere shortening.
 - Oxidants are also produced normally when we breathe, protection is provided by natural antioxidants; losing that protection can be one of the events in biological ageing. The human body protects itself from OS by using enzymatic antioxidant mechanisms.
 - A general description of an antioxidant (or a free-radical scavenger), is a molecule capable of decreasing or preventing the oxidation of other molecules.
 - I am a proponent of Pasqualino **not eating burnt, overcooked food**,
 - I also try to keep myself aware of research on the accumulation of Deleterious Mutations,
 - I am pitching a scientific imagination, imaginative reasoning (@pater_schoolofgiorgione_1877), as needed for that notion on an underlying biological mechanism(s) for our exposure - outcome theories I am pitching a scientific imagination as skeptical, statistical thinking (@tong_statisticalthinkingenables_2019) and causal thinking using a totality of the circumstances: you (positionality (kovach_2009)) have gathered on the exposures, outcomes, localities, positionalities.
- In my teaching of Causation, I have started to promote observation of a dose-response, a biological gradient, and reproducibility of, e.g., the dose-response observations. And notions on, fragments of knowledge on mechanisms,
 - Reproducibility is: we or another have to verify the relationship using a next step experiment design/observation design, new evidence. This is work that requires a testable theory based on a model(s) of the relationship (Theories). In addition, we need to include variance control measures, appropriate metrics for the relationship(s) and decisions on how to do the analysis.
 - We are looking for Causation, if we find something that can not establish causation we say so,

Figure 12: This Figure is an excerpt from https://bit.ly/MyNotes_Pasqualino> UpShot develop a Scientific Imagination(s)

Appendix 2. Using AutoGPT as a Research Assistant

Dear All

I hope you are well,

In CANVAS> Announcements> Note_51 I recommended you to consider using #AutoGPT as your #ResearchAssistant, I wrote ... 'AutoGPT: An Autonomous GPT-4 Experiment' by SigGravitas Date: 16th of April 2023, <https://github.com/Torantulino/Auto-GPT> is an excellent collaborating #researcher, ... I have it set up on My MacBook Pro and it is running wonderfully,

Below I post initial results from using AutoGPT> ... This being my fourth attempt at editing my language> **THE COINCIDENCE OF HEALTH DISPARITIES, VOLUME IV**

The set-up I wrote: Create an AI designed to autonomously develop and run an analysis of the health disparity border at 320 East 96th New York, NY 10128; the border exists because of a transition in the incidence of Asthma, the incidence being higher North of East 96th Street than South of, and the incidence of SarsCov2 related illness and deaths is higher North of East 96th Street than South?

- The GOALS I requested were:
 - **Why** do you think a health disparity border exists at this location such that the incidence of Asthma is higher north of this location than south of this location?
 - **Why** do you think a health disparity border exists at this location such that the incidence of SarsCov2-related illness and deaths is higher north of this location than south of this location?
 - **Why** the coincidence of two disease states at this location of the High Asthma incidence and the high incidence of SarsCov2-related illness and deaths?
 - How would you **investigate the coincidence** at this location?
 - **What are the root causes** of these two Health Disparities, Asthma Incidence and SarsCov2-related illness and death incidence?

Output from running this #AutoGPT:

THE COINCIDENCE OF HEALTH DISPARITIES, VOLUME IV

THE COINCIDENCE OF HEALTH DISPARITIES, VOLUME IV

THOUGHTS: I should start by investigating the existing literature on the health disparities in this location. I will start by searching on Google.

REASONING: Researching existing literature is a crucial first step in understanding the reasons behind a health disparity. Google is an excellent resource for this.

PLAN:

- Perform a Google search on the health disparity in this location.
- Read relevant articles and studies.
- Use AI Agents to analyze and summarize the available information.
- Circa 2025 I switched my AI Collaborator, Curator to Google Gemini 1.5 Flash and I investigating using DeepSeek.
- Develop hypotheses based on my findings.
- Investigate those hypotheses using data and further research.

CRITICISM: I need to remember to keep track of my research sources and findings in my files to avoid repeating my work in the future and crediting work-product.

NEXT ACTION: COMMAND = google ARGUMENTS = 'input': 'health disparities east 96th street new york'

Enter 'y' to authorise command, 'y -N' to run N continuous commands, 'n' to exit program, or enter feedback for The CoIncidence of Health Disparities, Volume IV...

Input: __

```

THE COINCIDENCE OF HEALTH DISPARITIES, VOLUME IV THOUGHTS: I should start
by investigating the existing literature on the health disparities in th
is location. I will start by searching on Google.
REASONING: Researching existing literature is a crucial first step in und
erstanding the reasons behind a health disparity. Google is an excellent
resource for this.
PLAN:
- Perform a Google search on the health disparity in this location.
- Read relevant articles and studies.
- Use GPT Agents to analyze and summarize the available information.
- Develop hypotheses based on my findings.
- Investigate those hypotheses using data and further research.
CRITICISM: I need to remember to keep track of my research sources and fi
ndings in my files to avoid repeating my work in the future.
NEXT ACTION: COMMAND = google ARGUMENTS = {'input': 'health disparities
east 96th street new york'}
Enter 'y' to authorise command, 'y -N' to run N continuous commands, 'n'
to exit program, or enter feedback for The CoIncidence of Health Disparit
ies, Volume IV...
Input: █
▣ session - moses  moses < Auto-GPT python3. > Moses Moses 14:46 28 - Apr - 23

```

Figure 13: #AutoGPT running at the COM-MANDLINE of iTerm2> THE COIN-CIDENCE OF HEALTH DISPARITIES, VOLUME IV

Appendix 3. Interlude: A Narrative-to-Data Framework for Mapping the Environmental Determinants of Immune Vulnerability

Abstract:

- Traditional epidemiological models often fail to capture the granular, real-time ‘Health Borders’ where environmental triggers and clinical vulnerabilities collide. This interlude proposes an evolution of the *Saving Lives* project, moving from an anecdotal collection of Narrative Interviews to a Systematic, Searchable Data Science framework.
 - Health Disparity Borders:
 - * In late Spring 2020 I thought I saw in the COVID-19 related deaths data a **Health Disparity Border** running along East 96th Street, it resonated with my experience of teaching at a school on East 96th between First and Second Avenue; the school, *Life Sciences Secondary School (LSSS)*, is on a **border** of Asthma hospitalizations for young people, I had prior knowledge of the incidence of Asthma hospitalizations.⁸² I highlighted this border in our slide show, Healthy Life Expectancies, <https://www.loom.com/share/80e92d3e79e1407f8bacod909be323eb>.
 - * I am presenting the **border** as a transition in the COVID-19 Disease hospitalization and death rate (circa 2020), and hospitalization rate related to Asthma (Circa 2000).
 - * I am speculating that there is an air pollution gradient and **border** running parallel with the COVID-19 Disease hospitalization and death rate, and the hospitalization rate related to Asthma.

⁸² My former Env. Sci. course, LSSS proposal, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1aYyTP9hLohcXiy4A4r7W5DZNHOKTCH/view?usp=sharing> <- just a historical marker for the origins of this document, ...you don't need this for the Assignment,

Consider can we develop an air pollution gradient map that can match the maps showing a gradient for COVID-19 Disease and Asthma. Limited resources mean we will not be measuring Air Pollutants. An available methodology is Senior High Schoolers interviewing Senior High Schoolers in an Environmental Science class on their encounters with Health, Bad Air Smells, Pollution, Asthma, Stories of Asthma. We will talk of trying to move anecdotal observations of environments to a systematic science by tagging the #NarrativeInterviews, e.g., #SmelledDiesel, #AHSurvivor. We will talk of investigating the health of Immune Systems around the 96th Street Health Disparity Border. See, Ural et al., 2022 ‘Inhaled particulate accumulation with age impairs immune function and architecture in human lung lymph nodes.’ Nature Medicine, 21 Nov. 2022, pp. 1-11, doi:10.1038/s41591-022-02073-x. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-022-02073-x> ...for assistance on mechanistic notions on exposure and outcome relationships.

- * If we are in a situation of limited resources the route to follow is a methodology of Senior High Schoolers interviewing Senior High Schoolers in an Environmental Science class on their encounters with Health, Bad Air Smells, Pollution, Asthma, Stories of Asthma.
- * When high-cost environmental sensors aren’t available, I develop methodologies that treat the community as the sensor - using structured narrative tagging to turn lived experiences into actionable clinical intelligence.
- * The Tagging Glossary: Systematic Science Metadata:
 - Central to this methodology is a Qualitative Metadata Schema, utilizing targeted hashtags (e.g., #AsthmaHospitalizationSurvivor, #AHSurvivor, #EnvironmentalBorder) to transform personal histories into structured, geocoded data. By tagging Narratives with specific clinical markers and environmental stressors (such as diesel corridors or ‘Health Borders’ akin to the South Bronx/Harlem/), we create a ‘Bottom-Up’ data stream.
 - This approach addresses the ‘Gatekeeper Science’ problem by empowering patients - particularly those from under-represented and undocumented communities - to contribute to a shareable, systematic database of modifiable root causes.
 - The resulting ‘Epistemic Community’ platform allows for the overlay of qualitative patient experience onto quantitative clinical records (e.g., HL7 FHIR standards or SNOMED CT coding) and environmental sensor data.

Metadata Tag	Category	Data Definition / Clinical Significance	Table 1: Tagging Glossary for Narrative-to-Data Systematic Science
#AHSurvivor	Clinical	Asthma Hospitalization Survivor: Indicates a history of acute respiratory distress requiring inpatient admission.	
#LupusFlare	Clinical	Autoimmune Activity: Self-reported period of increased systemic inflammation or symptomatic Disease activity.	
#SmelledDiesel	Exposure	Particulate Proxy: Qualitative detection of diesel exhaust; functions as a proxy for high NO ₂ /PM _{2.5} exposure in the absence of sensors.	
#RedRouteProximity	Exposure	Geospatial Risk: Narrative indicates residency or schooling within 50m of a major NYC Truck Corridor.	
#GatekeeperScience	Structural	Access Barrier: Narrative indicates a denial of diagnostic testing or environmental investigation by formal authorities.	
#HealthBorder	Structural	Disparity Marker: Indicates the event occurred at a known socioeconomic/environmental transition zone (e.g., <i>East 96th St</i>).	

This framework provides a blueprint for a consensus on the environmental determinants of disease, shifting the focus from reactive treatment to proactive, precision-based public health intervention. My hashtags like #AHSurvivor are essentially ‘User-Generated SNOMED codes.’ In a professional system, I would eventually map #AHSurvivor to the official SNOMED code for *Exacerbation of Asthma*.

- Building Infrastructure: The next step is evidenced by the publication of ‘*The Environmental Justice Matters Workshop*’ by Fischer, S., Holloman, S., Moses, K. (2025) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16049080> ... Building a Collaborative, an Epistemic Community is the path to take.

... This suggests to me you should all consider using #AI as a #ResearchAssistant, Curator.

I highly recommend you take over this search and take it further, the above is just first steps,

Ask me any questions you wish,

Best to you,

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